

Production quantities and C-sink potential of EBC-certified Biochar in 2023

Nikolas Hagemann^{1,2}, Vinayak Kamra^{1,2}, Hans-Peter Schmidt¹

¹Ithaka Institute, Arbaz, Switzerland and Goldbach, Germany

²Agroscope, Zurich, Switzerland

Published on February 19, 2024¹

Summary

The European Biochar Certificate (EBC)² guarantees sustainable sourcing of biomass, eco-friendly pyrolysis processes, and a save-to-use biochar. It is a producer and product certification scheme that is prerequisite for participation in most biochar-C-sink certification schemes. In 2023, 64×10^3 (sixty-four thousand) tons of EBC-certified biochar were produced in Europe (EU+EFTA³) using 261×10^3 tons of biomass. The biochar contained a total of 53×10^3 tons of carbon, which equals a C-sink potential of 0.195 Mt (megatons) CO₂e that is realized when the biochar is used non-oxidatively. When excluding all biochars with a molar hydrogen to organic carbon (H/C_{org}) ratio of ≥ 0.4 , the C-sink potential produced was 32×10^3 tons of carbon (0.116 Mt CO₂e).

¹ Please cite as: Hagemann N, Kamra V, Schmidt H-P: Production quantities and C-sink potential of EBC-certified Biochar in 2023. Ithaka Institute, 2024. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10679330>

² <https://www.european-biochar.org/en/ct/1>

³ 27 EU-member states + Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway and Switzerland as members of the European Free Trade Association

Introduction

Pyrogenic Carbon Capture and Storage (PyCCS) is an important negative emission technology that includes the production of biochar from sustainably sourced biomass and its non-oxidative use. However, the data on actual commercial production is scarce. Here, we evaluate the data generated by the certification process of the EBC standard, which is owned and operated by Carbon Standards International AG (Frick, Switzerland) and which grants exclusive access to this data to the Ithaka Institute. The primary data contains confidential information. The data is therefore published here in aggregated and anonymized form. Moreover, it enables market transparency via the partial disclosure of biochar properties.

Methods

We accessed the data used for EBC certification on December 15th, 2023. It included the following data sets for each batch of biochar:

- Expected biochar production [t]: Declared by the owner of the pyrolysis unit when creating the batch in dry matter.
- Expected biochar use [t]: Declared by the owner of the pyrolysis unit when creating the batch in dry matter.
- Biochar production [t]: Amount of biochar produced actually (dry matter), confirmed by external auditor.
- Biomass use [t]: Amount of biomass actually processed (dry matter), confirmed by external auditor
- Organic carbon content (C_{org}) [%] / [kg kg^{-1}] of the biochar, in mass percent of the dry matter.
- Molar ratio of hydrogen to organic carbon, molar H/C_{org} ratio [nondimensional].

The elemental composition is quantified from a representative sample of the batch, which is obtained as described in the EBC guidelines. Analysis is performed by an accredited lab. A batch of biochar is the amount of biochar that is produced from a homogenous feedstock under constant pyrolysis conditions for a maximum of 365 calendar days. Most pyrolysis units continuously produce biochar from a homogenous feedstock under constant pyrolysis conditions. In the latter cases, batches are only defined for the purpose of certification. Few pyrolysis facilities change their feedstock due to consumer preference or seasonality and thus have more than one batch per year.

We extracted the confirmed production quantity of the last completed batch, which was closed within the year 2023. If the batch was running for one year, the amount produced within the batch was considered the annual production in 2023 (t yr^{-1}). If the batch was produced for less than 365 days, it was checked that there was continuous production around the year. If this was confirmed, the annual production was calculated by dividing the production quantity by the duration of the batch (in days) and multiplied by 365 days yr^{-1} .

For new companies, that not yet completed their first batch of production, we used the expected amount of biochar to be produced and biomass to be processed as well as the expected duration. We have assumed constant production rate and have only considered the

share of expected production that would occur in 2023 if the batch were to run as planned until 2024. Only expected production using well-established technology was included; data from companies known to be in pilot phase with novel pyrolysis equipment were excluded. Data analysis revealed that the confirmed production quantity is on average 1.2 times the expected amount. Thus, using the expected amount of biochar with a factor of 1.0 results in a rather conservative and well-justified assumption.

The carbon sink (C-sink) potential here refers to the content of organic carbon in the biochar: the amount of biochar produced was multiplied with the organic carbon content. Please note that the guidelines of the EBC C-sink standard up to 2023 required that carbon expenditures, i.e. the direct and indirect emissions caused by the production, transport, and application of biochar, were subtracted from the C-sink potential. The data analysis presented here does not include carbon expenditures. Furthermore, in 2024, the EBC C-sink standard will be replaced by the Global Biochar C-sink standard⁴, which will require carbon expenditures to be offset with high quality C-sink certificates instead of the automatic deduction from the C-sink potential.

Results

The data on biochar production and resulting C-sink potentials (= organic carbon contents) is provided in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table 1: Data on biochar production

Region	Total biomass processed [t]	Total biochar produced [t]
EU+EFTA	261'482	64'106
Other Countries	22'637	4'931
Switzerland ^a	37'680	7'310

^a: also included in EU+EFTA data.

Table 2: Carbon Sink Potential

Region	All biochars		Biochar with H/C < 0.40	
	[t C]	[CO _{2e}]	[t C]	[CO _{2e}]
EU+EFTA	53'022	195 kt	31'691	116 kt
Other Countries	3'921	14.4 kt	1'176	4.3 kt
Switzerland ^a	5'975	21.9 kt	5'975	21.9 kt

^a: also included in EU+EFTA data.

⁴ www.carbon-standards.com

Discussion and Outlook

We assume that 60-80% of the biochar produced in Europe is EBC certified. For Switzerland, 100% can be assumed due to the *de facto* obligation to provide the certificate to the Federal Office for Agriculture.

Certification according to the EBC is available globally. However, due to the very high environmental standards and the very high level of technical development in Europe, some regulations are almost impossible for producers outside the EU to comply with, including e.g. the obligation to use excess heat in countries with tropical climates and a low level of industrialization. The market penetration of EBC is, therefore, significantly lower globally and difficult to estimate. Our dataset did not include any data e.g. from China.

On September 15, 2023, the guidelines for the World Biochar Certificate (WBC) were published as a sister program to the EBC. Certification according to the WBC is available world-wide, except for the EU/EFTA. WBC certified biochar must not be imported into the EU. In 2025, we aim to publish the combined EBC+WBC production data.

On October 5th, 2022, the guidelines for the Global Artisan C-Sink Certification were published to define how to certify carbon sinks generated with biochar made in an artisanal way, e.g. with pyrolysis in a Kon-Tiki, which is geographically limited to Low-Income, Lower Middle Income and Higher Middle Income countries as defined by the World Bank classification of countries. Consolidated data on biochar production within this program is not yet available. We also aim to publish Artisan production data in 2025.

Funding: This work was financially supported by the EJP Soil project CarboSeq, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No. 862695).